

Cite This Article: P. Bharathi & J. Vimala, "A Study on T-Fuzzy ℓ -Ideals in Lattice Ordered Group", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Special Issue, February, Page Number 83-86, 2017.

Abstract:

A lattice ordered group (ℓ -group) is a non-empty set G with binary operation $+$ and binary relation \leq such that $(G, +)$ is a group and (G, \leq) is a lattice. In this paper, we introduced the triangular norm (t-norm) on fuzzy ideals of an ℓ -group and some related results are investigated. We also discussed about an ℓ -homomorphism on T-fuzzy ℓ -ideals.

Key Words: ℓ -group, ℓ -homomorphism, Fuzzy ℓ -group, Fuzzy ℓ -ideal, t-norm & T-fuzzy ℓ -ideal

1. Introduction:

The concept of fuzzy sets was introduced by L. A. Zadeh [18] and it has been developed by several algebraists in many directions [7, 8, 9, 10, 13]. Rosenfeld [14] and Das [4] investigated the theory of fuzzy groups. N. Ajmal and K. V. Thomas [1] analyzed fuzzy lattices. The properties of lattices were studied in [5, 6]. Natarajan and Vimala [11, 12] introduced the theory of ideals in ℓ -groups and they presented many prominent results. G. S. V. Sathyaibaba [15] studied the concept of fuzzy lattice ordered groups as a mapping from ℓ -group into a complete lattice. He introduced L-fuzzy ℓ -ideals and proved some related results. Bharathi and Vimala [3] defined fuzzy ℓ -ideals of ℓ -group in new notion and they studied distributivity of fuzzy ℓ -ideals. Also, Vimala [17] investigated on homomorphism of fuzzy ℓ -ideals. Triangular norms (t-norms) were introduced by Schweizer and Sklar [16] due to the development of metric space theory. Now a day, t-norms contribute many applications in all fields of mathematics. In this paper, we introduced the concept of t-norms on fuzzy ℓ -ideals of ℓ -group. Also some properties of T-fuzzy ℓ -ideals are considered. In section II, we review some elementary definitions and results which are used to understand this paper. In section III, the notion of T-fuzzy ℓ -ideals is introduced and some related results are derived.

2. Preliminaries:

In this section, we have presented the basic definitions and results of ℓ -groups, ℓ -ideals, ℓ -homomorphism, fuzzy sets and fuzzy ℓ -groups which are useful for subsequent discussions.

Definition 2.1 [2] A non-empty set G is called a lattice ordered group (ℓ -group) iff

- (i) $(G, +)$ is a group
- (ii) (G, \leq) is a lattice
- (iii) $x \leq y$ implies $a+x+b \leq a+y+b$ for all x, y, a, b in G .

Definition 2.2 [2] Let G be an ℓ -group. A non-empty subset I of G is called an ℓ -ideal of G if

- (i) I is a subgroup of G .
- (ii) I is a sublattice of G .

Definition 2.3 [2] Let G, G' be two ℓ -groups. A function $f: G \rightarrow G'$ is called an ℓ -homomorphism if

- (i) $f(x \wedge y) = f(x) \wedge f(y)$
- (ii) $f(x \vee y) = f(x) \vee f(y)$.
- (iii) $f(x + y) = f(x) + f(y)$ for all $x, y \in G$.

Definition 2.4 [19] A fuzzy set of a non-empty set X is a function $\mu: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

Definition 2.5 [19] Let X be any non-empty set and μ be a fuzzy set defined on X and $t \in [0, 1]$. Then the set $\mu_t = \{x \in X / \mu(x) \geq t\}$ is called the level set of μ .

Definition 2.6 [19] Let X be any non-empty set and μ be a fuzzy set defined on X . Then the set $\{\mu(x) / x \in X\}$ is called the image of μ and is denoted by $\text{Im}(\mu)$

Definition 2.7 [19] Let X be any non-empty set and μ be a fuzzy set defined on X . The set $\{x / x \in X \text{ and } \mu(x) \geq 0\}$ is called the support of μ and it is denoted by $\text{supp}(\mu)$.

Definition 2.8 [15] Let $G = (G, +, \wedge, \vee)$ be an ℓ -group. A fuzzy set μ defined on G is said to be fuzzy lattice ordered group (fuzzy ℓ -group) of G if

- (i) $\mu(x+y) \geq \mu(x) \wedge \mu(y)$
- (ii) $\mu(-x) = \mu(x)$
- (iii) $\mu(x \vee y) \geq \mu(x) \wedge \mu(y)$
- (iv) $\mu(x \wedge y) \geq \mu(x) \wedge \mu(y)$ for all x, y in G .

Theorem 2.9 [15] Let G be an ℓ -group and μ be a fuzzy lattice ordered group. Then $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in G$.

Definition 2.10 [16] A t-norm is a function $T: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ that satisfies the following conditions for all $x, y, z \in [0, 1]$;

- (i) $T(x, 1) = x$
- (ii) $T(x, y) = T(y, x)$
- (iii) $T(x, T(y, z)) = T(T(x, y), z)$
- (iv) $T(x, y) \leq T(x, z)$ whenever $y \leq z$.

Theorem 2.11 [17] Let G_1, G_2 be two ℓ -groups and $f: G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ be the ℓ -homomorphism. Let μ_1 be the fuzzy ideal of G_1 and μ_2 be the fuzzy ideal of G_2 . Then the pre-image of f is defined by $[f^{-1}(\mu_2)](x) = \mu_2[f(x)]$ for $x \in G_1$.

3. T-Fuzzy ℓ -Ideals in ℓ -Group:

Definition 3.1 A fuzzy ℓ -ideal μ of an ℓ -group G is called T-fuzzy ℓ -ideal of G if

- (i) $\mu(x - y) \geq T(\mu(x), \mu(y))$
- (ii) $\mu(x \vee y) \geq T(\mu(x), \mu(y))$
- (iii) $\mu(x \wedge y) \geq T(\mu(x), \mu(y))$ for all $x, y \in G$.

Example 3.2 Consider the ℓ -group $(G, +, \vee, \wedge)$ such that $G = \{(x, y) / x, y \in \mathbb{Z}\}$. Define a fuzzy ℓ -ideal μ on G such that $\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.5 & \text{if } y = 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } y \neq 0 \end{cases}$ and define a t-norm T such that

$T(x, y) = \max(x+y-1, 0)$. Then μ is a T-fuzzy ℓ -ideal of G .

Definition 3.3 A fuzzy ℓ -group μ of an ℓ -group G is said to be T-fuzzy ℓ -group if

- (i) $\mu(x - y) \geq T(\mu(x), \mu(y))$
- (ii) $\mu(x \vee y) \geq T(\mu(x), \mu(y))$
- (iii) $\mu(x \wedge y) \geq T(\mu(x), \mu(y))$ for all $x, y \in G$.

Now we state the following theorems without proof as they are obvious.

Theorem 3.4 Every T-fuzzy ℓ -ideal of an ℓ -group G is a T-fuzzy ℓ -group of G . But the converse need not be true.

Theorem 3.5 A fuzzy set μ of G is the T-fuzzy ℓ -ideal of G if and only if the level set $\mu_t = \{x \in G / \mu(x) \geq t\}$ is an ℓ -ideal of G when it is non-empty.

Then we have the following theorems related to ℓ -homomorphism on T-fuzzy ℓ -ideals.

Theorem 3.6 Let G_1, G_2 be two ℓ -groups and $f : G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ be the ℓ -homomorphism. Let μ_1 be the T-fuzzy ℓ -ideal of G_1 . Then there exist a T-fuzzy ℓ -ideal μ_2 of G_2 such that $\mu_2[f(x)] = \mu_1(x)$ for all $x \in G$.

Proof:

For any $x_1, x_2 \in G_1$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i)} \quad \mu_2[f(x_1) - f(x_2)] &= \mu_2[f(x_1 - x_2)] \\ &= \mu_1(x_1 - x_2) \\ &\geq T(\mu_1(x_1), \mu_1(x_2)) \\ &= T(\mu_2(f(x_1)), \mu_2(f(x_2))) \\ \Rightarrow \mu_2[f(x_1) - f(x_2)] &\geq T(\mu_2(f(x_1)), \mu_2(f(x_2))) \\ \text{(ii)} \quad \mu_2[f(x_1) \wedge f(x_2)] &= \mu_2[f(x_1 \wedge x_2)] \\ &= \mu_1(x_1 \wedge x_2) \\ &\geq T(\mu_1(x_1), \mu_1(x_2)) \\ &= T(\mu_2(f(x_1)), \mu_2(f(x_2))) \\ \Rightarrow \mu_2[f(x_1) \wedge f(x_2)] &\geq T(\mu_2(f(x_1)), \mu_2(f(x_2))) \\ \text{(iii)} \quad \mu_2[f(x_1) \vee f(x_2)] &= \mu_2[f(x_1 \vee x_2)] \\ &= \mu_1(x_1 \vee x_2) \\ &\geq T(\mu_1(x_1), \mu_1(x_2)) \\ &= T(\mu_2(f(x_1)), \mu_2(f(x_2))) \\ \Rightarrow \mu_2[f(x_1) \vee f(x_2)] &\geq T(\mu_2(f(x_1)), \mu_2(f(x_2))) \end{aligned}$$

Hence μ_2 is a T-fuzzy ℓ -ideal of G_2 .

Theorem 3.7 Let G_1, G_2 be two ℓ -groups and $f : G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ be the ℓ -homomorphism. Let μ_1 be the T-fuzzy ℓ -ideal of G_1 and μ_2 be the T-fuzzy ℓ -ideal of G_2 . Then the pre-image of f defined by $[f^{-1}(\mu_2)](x) = \mu_2[f(x)]$ is a T-fuzzy ℓ -ideal of G_1 .

Proof:

For any $x, y \in G_1$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i)} \quad [f^{-1}(\mu_2)](x - y) &= \mu_2[f(x - y)] \\ &= \mu_2[f(x) - f(y)] \\ &\geq T(\mu_2[f(x)], \mu_2[f(y)]) \\ &= T(f^{-1}(\mu_2)(x), f^{-1}(\mu_2)(y)) \\ \Rightarrow [f^{-1}(\mu_2)](x - y) &\geq T(f^{-1}(\mu_2)(x), f^{-1}(\mu_2)(y)) \\ \text{(ii)} \quad [f^{-1}(\mu_2)](x \wedge y) &= \mu_2[f(x \wedge y)] \\ &= \mu_2[f(x) \wedge f(y)] \\ &\geq T(\mu_2[f(x)], \mu_2[f(y)]) \\ &= T(f^{-1}(\mu_2)(x), f^{-1}(\mu_2)(y)) \\ \Rightarrow [f^{-1}(\mu_2)](x \wedge y) &\geq T(f^{-1}(\mu_2)(x), f^{-1}(\mu_2)(y)) \\ \text{(iii)} \quad [f^{-1}(\mu_2)](x \vee y) &= \mu_2[f(x \vee y)] \\ &= \mu_2[f(x) \vee f(y)] \\ &\geq T(\mu_2[f(x)], \mu_2[f(y)]) \\ &= T(f^{-1}(\mu_2)(x), f^{-1}(\mu_2)(y)) \\ \Rightarrow [f^{-1}(\mu_2)](x \vee y) &\geq T(f^{-1}(\mu_2)(x), f^{-1}(\mu_2)(y)) \end{aligned}$$

Thus the pre-image of f is a T-fuzzy ℓ -ideal of G_1 .

Theorem 3.8 Let μ be the T-fuzzy ℓ -ideal of an ℓ -group G . Then the fuzzy set $\varphi : \frac{G}{\mu} \rightarrow [0,1]$ defined by $\varphi(g + \mu) = \mu(g)$ is the T-fuzzy ℓ -ideal of $\frac{G}{\mu}$.

Proof:

Let $g_1, g_2 \in G$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i)} \quad \varphi[(g_1 + \mu) - (g_2 + \mu)] &= \varphi[(g_1 - g_2) + \mu] \\ &= \mu(g_1 - g_2) \\ &\geq T(\mu(g_1), \mu(g_1)) \\ &= T(\varphi(g_1 + \mu), \varphi(g_2 + \mu)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \varphi[(g_1 + \mu) - (g_2 + \mu)] \geq T(\varphi(g_1 + \mu), \varphi(g_2 + \mu))$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(ii)} \quad \varphi[(g_1 + \mu) \vee (g_2 + \mu)] &= \varphi[(g_1 \vee g_2) + \mu] \\ &= \mu(g_1 \vee g_2) \\ &\geq T(\mu(g_1), \mu(g_1)) \\ &= T(\varphi(g_1 + \mu), \varphi(g_2 + \mu)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \varphi[(g_1 + \mu) \vee (g_2 + \mu)] \geq T(\varphi(g_1 + \mu), \varphi(g_2 + \mu))$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(iii)} \quad \varphi[(g_1 + \mu) \wedge (g_2 + \mu)] &= \varphi[(g_1 \wedge g_2) + \mu] \\ &= \mu(g_1 \wedge g_2) \\ &\geq T(\mu(g_1), \mu(g_1)) \\ &= T(\varphi(g_1 + \mu), \varphi(g_2 + \mu)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \varphi[(g_1 + \mu) \wedge (g_2 + \mu)] \geq T(\varphi(g_1 + \mu), \varphi(g_2 + \mu))$$

Theorem 3.9 Let G be an ℓ -group and I be an ℓ -ideal of G . If μ is a T-fuzzy ℓ -ideal of G/I then there exists a T-fuzzy ℓ -ideal φ of G such that $\varphi_t = I$ for $t = \mu(0)$.

Proof:

Let $x, y \in G$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i)} \quad \varphi(x - y) &= \mu((x - y) + I) \\ &= \mu((x + I) - (y + I)) \\ &\geq T(\mu((x + I), (y + I))) \\ &= T(\varphi(x), \varphi(y)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \varphi(x - y) \geq T(\varphi(x), \varphi(y))$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(ii)} \quad \varphi(x \vee y) &= \mu((x \vee y) + I) \\ &= \mu((x + I) \vee (y + I)) \\ &\geq T(\mu((x + I), (y + I))) \\ &= T(\varphi(x), \varphi(y)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \varphi(x \vee y) \geq T(\varphi(x), \varphi(y))$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(iii)} \quad \varphi(x \wedge y) &= \mu((x \wedge y) + I) \\ &= \mu((x + I) \wedge (y + I)) \\ &\geq T(\mu((x + I), (y + I))) \\ &= T(\varphi(x), \varphi(y)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \varphi(x \wedge y) \geq T(\varphi(x), \varphi(y))$$

Let $x \in \varphi_t$ for $t = \mu(0)$

$$\Leftrightarrow \varphi(x) = (0)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \mu(x + I) = \mu(0 + I) = \mu(I)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow x \in I$$

Hence $\varphi_t = I$ for $t = \mu(0)$.

Conclusion:

In this paper, the concept of T-fuzzy ℓ -ideals has been inspected. This work absorbed on some properties of T-fuzzy ℓ -ideals of an ℓ -group. In future, we can extend this notion to T-fuzzy prime ideals, T-fuzzy quotient ideals, etc.

Acknowledgement:

Authors are very grateful to the referees for their valuable comments and suggestions.

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